

SYMBOL	NAME	CHARACTERISTICS	WHO PAYS WHAT?
	GOLD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publishing in OA journals • Licence (most commonly Creative Commons) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No cost for readers. • Authors or their institutions pay a fee (APC) • The cost of maintaining infrastructure is borne by publishers.
	GREEN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-archiving • Licence (usually Creative Commons) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No cost for readers. • The cost of maintaining infrastructure is borne by repository owners. • No cost for publishers.
N/A	DIAMOND / PLATINUM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publishing in OA journals • Licence (usually Creative Commons) • Also referred to as APC-free OA, no-fee OA, publisher-pays model 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No cost for readers. • No cost for authors and their institution. • The cost of maintaining infrastructure is borne by publishers (and/or their sponsors).
	BRONZE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free to read • All rights reserved, implied or explicit • Not really OA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No cost for readers. • In most cases, no cost for authors and their institutions. • The cost of maintaining infrastructure is borne by publishers (and/or their sponsors).
N/A	HYBRID	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publishing in subscription-based journals with an Open Access option • Licence (most commonly Creative Commons) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No cost for readers for OA articles, but no discount for the non-OA content. • Authors or their institutions pay a fee (APC) • The cost of maintaining infrastructure is borne by publishers.
	BLACK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Illegal piracy websites • Copyright violation by posting copyrighted content on social media (ResearchGate, Academia.edu, etc.) • Not really OA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No cost for readers. • No cost for authors and their institution. • Publishers bear the cost of infrastructure and legal proceedings against copyright infringement. • Platforms offering copyrighted content illegally bear the cost of the underlying infrastructure and legal proceedings against copyright infringement.

Slide from the presentation “Open Access beyond Gold and Green”, OpenAIRE Open Science Bootcamp, 6-10 June 2022.

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